

An Overview of Nanotechnology Used in the Food Industries

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Abstract: Food packaging is critical for getting food from farm to fork. Improper packaging, such as food decaying from lack of wrapping, condiments sticking to containers, or the difficulty to portion fresh bulk products for timely consumption, accounts for 25% of household food waste. Packaging that prevents spoiling or extends shelf life can save 280,000 tonnes of food, worth \$882 million. Food supply chain losses plague developing nations. Proper packing can protect and preserve food so it can reach these families securely. This review discusses nanoparticles used in food packaging instead of conventional ways. It also discusses nanoparticle health risks and antibacterial characteristics.

Index Terms - Nanoparticles, Nanocomposites, Food Industry, Shelf life, Food Packaging

I. INTRODUCTION

Food manufacturing is centred on food packaging, which has become the only reliable way to ensure food quality. Packaging plays a crucial role in the food manufacturing process. Packaging materials have a number of significant uses in the food sector, including the prevention of waste, the reduction of the need for preservatives, and the reduction of rotting. Despite doing a good job of ensuring food quality, the main shortcomings of conventional food packaging systems are their inefficient microbial growth control. [1]

Nanotechnology develops, characterises, and employs structures between 1 and 100 nm in size. The engineering, healthcare, agricultural, and food industries have all been profoundly influenced by this cutting-edge technology. When compared to conventional food processing methods, nanomaterials offer considerable promise for increasing the shelf life of food while also reducing the risk of infection. The toxicity of nanoparticles and nanomaterials is unknown, despite the rapid growth of nanotechnology in food products. Given the ever-increasing need for food scientists, it is imperative that nanomaterials be fully described and their usage be effectively controlled. [2]

Nanotechnology-based food packaging provides various benefits over conventional packaging methods, including improved resistance to temperature, increased durability, decreased flammability, and more efficient material dispersion in a biological system. Nanocomposite materials have advanced, and as a result, they are now widely employed, particularly in the food and packaging sectors. They work well for covering fruits to keep them fresh longer and postpone ripening. [3] Figure 1 provides examples of how nanomaterials are used in the food sector.:

Fig.1: Nanotechnology's Role in the Food Industry: A Simplified Flowchart

Innovative packaging materials have been developed in response to both technological advancements and consumer demand for food that is both healthy and long-lasting.[4] As a result of advancements in barrier qualities, new product categories have been able to be developed; nevertheless, the manufacturing costs and recycling challenges associated with such packaging have made it less popular.[5] Consequently, it is preferable to build monolayer packaging with improved characteristics, reduced weight, transparency, and recyclable or biocompatible, and this is feasible thanks to advancements in nanotechnology.[6]

Nanotechnology may be used to build active packaging, which preserves food through processes triggered by either internal or external variables, as well as intelligent packaging, that offers data on the true status of the food.[7] Direct interaction between nanoparticles and pathogenic cells and the transmission of antimicrobial compounds like metal ions and reactive oxygen compounds are necessary for active packaging to demonstrate antibacterial effect; however, the release of such antimicrobial compounds must be regulated, and the migratory movement of the nanoparticle is also undesired due to its unpredictable impacts on the human body.[8],[9]

The effectiveness of nanotechnology's packaging applications is used to divide them into several classes. Most of the nanoparticles employed in food packaging have antimicrobial properties, either because they themselves are antimicrobial or because they serve as vehicles for antimicrobial polypeptides that prevent food spoilage. In packaging materials comprised of a coating of starch colloids infused with the antimicrobial agent, the deliberate dispersion of antimicrobials via the packed product works as a barrier to bacteria. There is evidence that novel nano-antimicrobial compounds can delay food spoilage and lengthen its shelf life. Nanoparticles of multiple distinct metals and metal oxides are being considered as potential antibacterial agents. Reactive oxygen species are produced more readily as a result of their innate physicochemical traits, which leads to oxidative stress and eventual bacterial cell destruction.[10],[11] The following table lists the various nano-techniques along with the materials used in these techniques in the food industry:

Nanotechnique	Materials		Application	References
Nanoparticles		Carrier	Food Packaging	
	a. Titanium NP,	Low-density polyethylene, Polyethylene	Strawberries	[12]–[14]
	b. Zinc NP,	Low-density polyethylene, Allyl isothiocyanate, nisin, Polyvinyl chloride, Bacterial cellulose	Chicken thigh, egg albumen, Orange juice	[14]–[16]
c. Copper NP,	Cellulose absorber	Fruit Juices such as melons, apples, pineapple	[17]	

	d. Silver NP	Low-density polyethylene, Absorbent and Cellulose pad, Polyvinylpyrrolidone, Chitosan	Fruit Juices, poultry meat, Fresh cut fruits, mushrooms	[13] , [15] , [18] – [21]
Nanosensors	Metal based nanosensors, Nanobiosensors, Nano-smart dust, Nanobarcodes		Food Packaging	[22] , [23]
Nanocomposites		Carrier	Food Packaging	[24] , [25]
	a. Nanoclay	Carboxymethyl cellulose polyvinyl alcohol films	Walnuts, Beer	
	b. Carbon nanotubes	Polyethylene, allyl isothiocyanate	Dates, Meat	[3] , [26]
Nano-encapsulation	Nanocentrals, nanocapsules, colloidosomes		Food Processing	[2]

Table 1: List of Nanotechniques used in the Food Industry

II. FOOD PACKAGING

Nanocomposites:

- Nanonoclay:

Platelet-shaped nanoclays have a cracked, fragile structure and low specific gravity. They also have a high dimension ratio owing to their thickness. Montmorillonite and organophilic MMT, In particular, two of these nanoclays have garnered a lot of interest in the packaging sector thanks to their high expanse, wide aspect ratio, and good compliance with the vast majority of organic thermoplastics.[\[27\]](#), [\[28\]](#) It is frequently utilised to increase the visible characteristics of plastic packaging, including its barriers against moisture and gas. MMT consists of an octahedral film of aluminium hydroxide between two layers of tetrahedral silica. Given its high cation exchange efficacy, large surface area, and favourable swelling behaviour, it has found widespread usage in composite materials.[\[29\]](#) Tactoid, intercalated, and exfoliated are the three categories used to describe the nanoclay dispersion pattern in the polymer matrix. Nanoclay composites generally have either an intercalated or exfoliated structure, depending on how uniformly the nanoparticles are dispersed throughout the polymer framework.[\[30\]](#), [\[31\]](#)

According to a study, adding nanoclay to the bottles extended the beer's storage period from 77 to 210 days. According to research, nanoclays make packaging thicker, lower gas permeability, and diminish oxygen-dependent foods in nylons and plastic bottles. A nanocomposite coating with 3 per cent nanoclay was shown to be a potential packaging material for walnuts in a study. There is also room for improvement in the properties' ability to resist gas incursion.[\[25\]](#), [\[32\]](#).

- Carbon Nanotubes:

One of the latest noteworthy advanced carbon nanomaterials, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), are currently attracting a great deal of attention in the global modern food-packaging market. This is owing to the fact that CNTs offer a number of amazing benefits, such as a huge surface area-to-volume ratio, facile functionalisation, marvellous physicochemical and water repellent capabilities, high thermal and electrical conductivity, excellent adsorption ability, excellent antibacterial activity, among other things that Better evaluations of packaging design, product quality, freshness, safety, and security are possible with CNT-based nanosensors.[\[23\]](#)

These nanotubes may be generated as either single- or multi-walled carbon atoms and have diameters between 1 nm and over 100 nm, depending on the context in which they will be used. Polymers with added CNTs have improved properties that make them suitable for usage in the packaging sector. Since CNTs can break the membrane of a cell and so cause irreparable harm to a microbial cell, they are inherently anti-bacterial.[\[10\]](#)

During an analysis of the packaging of Mazafati dates, it was discovered that the use of CNT combined with polyethylene films significantly extended the dates' durability. CNT and allyl isothiocyanate have been investigated for their potential use in the packaging of meat. It was essentially an airtight container designed to keep cooked food safe from bacteria. It was basically an

antimicrobial packaging for storing cooked food. CNT, when combined with allyl isothiocyanate and *Salmonella choleraesuis*, are a reliable means of preserving food for up to 40 days.[3], [26]

Nanoparticles:

- Titanium NP

TiO₂-NPs are considered to be valuable metal oxide nanoparticles because of their thermostability and inertia, and they are among the materials that have been researched the most. Biodegradable films can have their properties modified by the material, making them cheaper, less poisonous, and more resistant to light.[1] The ability of TiO₂ nanostructures to self-destruct was the focus of a lot of people's attention. They are useful in food processing and packing owing to this feature. It is commonly employed as a photocatalyst in food packing, and it has many applications in the fields of economics and the environment, including air and water cleansing, antimicrobial, self-cleaning properties, and water filtering.[30], [33]

TiO₂ nanoparticles can be made using diverse processes, however sol-gel manufacturing is the most highly used one. Due to its effective short-wavelength light absorption and high photostability, TiO₂ is a semiconductor that got a lot of publicity. In addition to maintaining the high transparency of polymeric films used for food packaging, adding TiO₂ nanoparticles also prevents UV radiation from having a negative impact on food ingredients.[10], [34] In a study, tests were done on nanocomposites' ability to resist *Pseudomonas* species, *E. coli*, and *Rhodotorula mucilaginosa*. The bactericidal effectiveness rose as TiO₂ load on the CA matrix increased. The amount of *E. coli* decreased by 1.69 log CFU/ml after adding 5% TiO₂ to a CA matrix. When added to PLA and PCL, TiO₂ failed to substantially limit the development of *E. coli*. UV-A irradiation of TiO₂-PLA and TiO₂-PCL nanocomposites did not substantially decrease the quantities of *Pseudomonas spp.* and *Rhodotorula mucilaginosa*. [35]

Food packaging often includes TiO₂ as a pigment or coating element. Visible light is effectively scattered by the white TiO₂ particles, imparting strength, shine, and whiteness to whatever is covered with it. TiO₂ NPs are typically added to PET and HDPE bottles for pasteurised milk packing to lessen the detrimental impact of light on milk quality. TiO₂ is absolutely inert, non-flammable, and completely impermeable to any and all edible substances as a thin coating in solid form.[34], [36] TiO₂ nanoparticles' photocatalytic activity results in self-cleaning characteristics and, as a result, antibacterial effects when exposed to UVA or black light. In order to utilise nanocomposite materials for biocidal purposes in food packaging, TiO₂ was incorporated into chitosan and ethylene-vinyl alcohol.[37], [38]

- Zinc NP

Broad-spectrum bacterial species are effectively suppressed from growing by ZnO-NPs, which have a variety of morphologies.[39] ZnO-NPs are more readily available and less expensive than AgNPs, making them an especially appealing material for packaging applications. In addition, ZnO can generate a significant amount of hydrogen peroxide when exposed to UV radiation, which can make bacterial cells more susceptible to oxidative stress.[24] Numerous studies show that zinc ions are more efficient in preventing bacterial growth (bacteriostasis) than in killing them (bactericidal).[30]

Polymeric films can considerably improve their packaging's blockage qualities, mechanical strength, and durability by absorbing zinc oxide nanoparticles.[40] According to a study, the polylactic acid (PLA) matrix's well-distributed zinc oxide nanoparticles significantly increased the tortuosity of the diffusive pathway, which decreased the susceptibility of penetrant molecules through PLA.[41]

Given zinc oxide's antibacterial effectiveness is correlated with its concentration, altering the concentration of ZnO is likely to have bactericidal effects. *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Staphylococcus aureus* have been demonstrated to be inhibited by ZnO-NPs in cooked poultry.[42] They may also have the ability to shield food from bacterial contamination.[43] Decomposition markers such as malondialdehyde (MDA), ethylene, polyphenol oxidase and POD activity are also used to evaluate newly cut apples. According to a study, the remodelling of BC-PPy-ZnO nanocomposite films might reduce pH rise while also preventing microbiological growth in chicken thighs. Thus, its storage period lengthens. [44] Under UV exposure, ZnONPs can oxidise ethylene into H₂O and CO₂ and lower the activity of polyphenol oxidase, POD, and MDA buildup. This technique enables the employment of MAP with PVC-ZnO-nanocomposite films to increase the life-span of goods.[10], [40], [45]

- Copper NP

Copper nanoparticles (NPs) are widely utilised as catalysts, components of optics, antibiotics, fungicides, and conducting agents due to their unique physical and biological features.[46] Hydrazine carboxylate of copper (II) in liquid can be reduced using two thermal and sonochemical techniques to get copper nanoparticles. In addition, changing the pH, temperature, reducing agents, and solvent can bring about the creation of particles with varied sizes, shapes, morphologies, and properties.[10], [17]

Because of their high surface-to-volume ratio, reaction time, and optimal release properties, CuNPs may effectively combine with polymeric matrix and exhibit biotechnological effects, according to studies. In a study employing process of melting and mixing, the impacts of HDPE+Cunanofibers (0.5, 1 and 5%) were investigated. Results demonstrated that HDDPE with higher concentrations of Cu NPs considerably improved antibacterial properties against *Escherichia coli* DHSa, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* BS3, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. [47], [48] In addition to the boosts in tension strength, Young's modulus, and oxygen impermeability, these side effects were also observed.[49]

- Silver NP

Given that they have a greater surface area per mass than micro-scale silver particles or bulk silver content, AgNPs, which are typically metallic silver meant for sterilisation, exhibit antibacterial, anti-yeast, anti-fungal, and anti-viral properties.[50], [51] Additionally, AgNPs can bind to the surface of cells and degrade lipopolysaccharides, resulting in a crater in the cell membrane. AgNPs can be packaged in a wide variety of polymeric polymers.[52] Ex situ and in situ techniques can be used to create silver nanoparticles. The ex-situ method entails spreading reduced silver nanoparticles in the polymerisable formulation after first reducing them with borohydride. This method's drawback is its inability to control monodispersed nanoparticles. In contrast, utilising precursors with excellent dispersibility, the in situ technique can create nanoparticles in a setting that is conducive to polymerization.[10], [53]

Whether it's a non-biodegradable polymerized film like PE, PVC, or EVOH, or a biodegradable coated film formed by a polymer or stabilizer (eco-friendly packaging), silver nanoparticles in active packaging interact directly with the polymer framework. Due to their high stability and prolonged release rates of silver ions in preserved foods, Ag-NPs are also a great choice for use in food packaging.[54] Accordingly, a study[55] showed the antimicrobial activity of a substance made of cellulose nanofibrils and Ag-NPs against *L. monocytogenes* and *E. coli*. *A. niger*, *P. citrinum*, *S. aureus*, and *E. coli* all demonstrated good growth inhibitory action when silver nanoparticles were fixed with laponite.[56]

Direct harm to cell walls and membranes is an elementary technique for Ag-NP' antibacterial effectiveness that has been proposed. Its antibacterial activity is caused by the interaction of metallic Ag-NPs with aqueous O and H ions.[57], [58] The antibacterial effectiveness of Ag-NP is significantly influenced by the oxidised surface of the silver atoms.[59] It was hypothesised that Ag-NPs' intrusion with cell-membrane activity and reactive oxygen was a major mechanism for the antibacterial action.[60] Silver nanoparticles are also ingested by cells because of their small size, where they release Ag ions that interfere with DNA replication and ATP synthesis via a Trojan horse mechanism.[61] The availability of silver ion exposure to bacteria thereby affects their antimicrobial efficacy.[62]

III. FOOD PROCESSING

Food processing is the art of preserving food via the use of various processes and approaches so that it may be consumed at a later point in time. These approaches have been established to stop the spread of harmful pathogens while preserving the food's natural taste and quality.[63] Some of the classical processing techniques for food include irradiation, heating, pickling, smoking, etc. Some examples of how nanoparticles are utilised in the food industry include the addition of nutraceuticals; the delivery of nutrients; the addition of minerals and vitamins; and the encapsulation of tastes.[64] Toxins are eliminated, infections are prevented, food is preserved, and food homogeneity is increased to facilitate better marketing and distribution through processing. When transporting food from the source to the consumer across great distances, processed goods have a longer shelf life and are therefore more desirable.[2], [65]

- Nanoencapsulation

Nanocomposite, nano-emulsification, and nanostructures are all examples of nanoencapsulation processes, and they all contribute to the end product's functioning by allowing the deliberate release of the core material. This method can be used to create functional meals with increased functionality and stability by protecting bioactive ingredients including vitamins, antioxidants, peptides, fats, and starches.[66]

In addition to boosting bioavailability and efficacy, these have a number of other benefits, such as being easier to work with, more stable, protecting against oxidation, retaining volatile elements, improving taste, releasing in stages in response to changes in moisture or pH, delivering multiple active ingredients at once, altering taste character, extending organoleptic perception, and so on.[67] The substance is contained in a reserve that is encompassed by a polymeric membrane, and these systems may be thought of as nano vesicular ones since they have a classic core-shell architecture.[68] Six basic techniques are used to create nanocapsules; they are nanoprecipitation, emulsion-diffusion, double emulsification, emulsion-coacervation, polymer coating, and layer-by-layer. They serve to increase the nutritional value of foods by using natural, lipophilic substances such as vitamins, minerals, essential fats, and growth hormones. Encapsulation's main perk is that it conceals the component, making it more likely to arrive at the intended location even if the environmental factors are less than ideal.[69]

The effectiveness of antioxidants is increased via lipid-based nanoencapsulation strategies, which increase their dissolution and absorption, in both in vitro and in vivo sustainability, and limit their undesirable interplay with various other important dietary nutrients. Nanoliposomes, nanocochleates, and archaeosomes are the principal lipid-based nanoencapsulation mechanisms that may be employed for the preservation and distribution of meals and nutraceuticals.[70] Nanoencapsulation frequently makes use of nano-based carriers like liposomes. Using nanoliposomes, the system's components may be dispersed in a controlled and precise manner. Several different kinds of nutraceuticals, minerals, enzymes, vitamins, antimicrobials, and additives are thought to be transported by them.[71]

It was hypothesized, during research, that a technology may be developed to create water-soluble nanoparticles with regulated functionality that captured beta-carotene. The ordinarily hydrophobic beta-carotene was synthesised by scientists within a lipid nanocarrier. Because of this, beta-carotene can be readily disseminated and stabilised in drinks, despite its generally hydrophobic nature.[72] The prolamine zein found in maize endosperm binds and encases fats, protecting them from oxidation. Zein's adsorption of fatty acids has also been demonstrated to result in the formation of intriguing nanolayers of collaboratively constructed FA and zein sheets. Research is being done on a novel encapsulation technology in which zein fibres are filled with gallic acid through

electrospinning. In this method, both the original characteristics of the meal and the system's missing ingredients are preserved through the minimal interaction between the two.[73], [74]

The production of hydrophilic nanodispersions with large quantities of components impermeable to water relies heavily on soy lecithin. Nutraceuticals that do not dissolve in water, vitamins that are fat-soluble, and flavours are all examples of such substances.[75] All of the benefits of the encapsulated actives, such as greater stability and bioavailability, are maintained during the process of dispersing them into water-based formulations. In an effort to create vaccinations that can control the body's immunological response, nanotechnology is also being used in a new sector called nanoencapsulation of probiotics. The nanoencapsulation of probiotics is a promising new use of nanotechnology, as it represents an attempt to create vaccines capable of modulating the body's immunological response. Nanoencapsulation is ideally suited for the development of targeted probiotic microbial formulations that are able to be administered to specific regions of the GI tract and engage with particular receptors.[76] It is possible that these nano-encapsulated designer probiotic bacterial formulations can modulate immune responses in the same way that de novo vaccines do.

Many studies have shown that starch-like nanoparticles can efficiently convey their cargo to specific locations within a living organism, aiding in the maintenance of lipid bodies in the process. Antioxidants can be delivered using nano-encapsulated delivery methods like archaeosomes. Lipid bilayers from archaeobacteria provide the raw material for these.[77] These lipids have been found to be stress- and heat-resistant. According to certain studies, nano-encapsulating α -tocopherol in fat droplets can prevent milk from deteriorating.[6]

- Nanoemulsions

Nanoemulsions are used in the manufacturing of many processed goods, including condiments for salads, scented oils, sugar substitutes, individualized beverages, and more. They aid in the release of various flavours by using various stimuli.[78] They effectively inhibit oxidation and enzymatic processes, hence preserving the flavours. There are primarily two methods that nanoemulsions are created; the first, the high-energy technique and the low-energy method.[79]

The liquid phase is dispersed in a sustained aqueous environment to produce the nanoemulsions. Lipophilic ingredients are employed to make nanoemulsions, and the oil phase is extensively mixed with the lipophilic ingredient.[80] Hydrophobicity, surface activity, the oil-water partition coefficient, dissolution, and melting point are only few of the variables that affect this procedure. Many lipophilic compounds, such as α -carotene, capsaicin, flaxseed oil, coenzyme Q, and various oil-soluble vitamins, can be encapsulated using nanoemulsions.[81]

They can be used to reduce surface contaminants of chicken skin and to clean the surfaces of food processing facilities. *Salmonella typhimurium* colony expansion was halted by nanoemulsion. Based on the microencapsulated fish oil's physicochemical properties, sugar beetroot pectin should be considered as a possible replacement for the proteins found in milk and gum Arabic in the encapsulation of nutritious food components.[82], [83] The nanoemulsions showed tremendous guarantee of usage in beverages, etc. Single-layer nanoemulsions, double-layer nanoemulsions, and triple-layer nanoemulsions are all possible depending on the polyelectrolytes used.[67]

Nowadays, nanoemulsions are chosen over conventional ones because they will be more quickly absorbed and because they will be more quickly absorbed and will be more digestible by the digestive enzymes as a result of the greater surface area per droplet and the smaller droplet size.[84] In the small intestine, emulsions that are smaller have a better chance of penetrating the mucous barrier. Since they are smaller, emulsions have the benefit of being carried over the epithelial layer, which aids in greater adsorption of the constituents. The smaller the lipophilic components are, the more soluble they become. In essence, nanoemulsions became well-known as a method of delivering phytochemicals. Carotenoids and polyphenols are the two primary phytochemicals that lower blood pressure, reduce components that cause cancer, control the digestive tract, increase resistance to disease, control blood sugar and cholesterol, and act as phytonutrients.[85]–[87] Yet, the manufacturers' biggest concern was that these phytochemicals weren't adequately bioavailable. By creating effective delivery mechanisms, nanoemulsions increased the bioavailability of the phytochemicals and made this improbable task practicable. The bioavailability of the phytochemicals increases with the size of the lipids.[88]

- Anti-caking Agents

Due to the production of lumps and agglomerates, caking of food powders affects the functioning and quality of goods. Furthermore, caking reduces food storage life and promotes the loss of flavor and texture by influencing the ease with which food rehydrates and disperses.[89], [90] The creation of liquid bridges between crystals, either by partial deliquescence or condensation, is the first step in the caking process in crystalline materials driven by external moisture.[90], [91] Anticaking agents can work in a number of ways, such as by making the host powder less water-retentive, coating particles with moisture-resistant layers, providing a smooth texture to reduce friction between particles, and preventing crystal growth.

SiO₂ preserves the flow properties of powdered goods including icing sugar, dried milk, and dry mixes. It also acts as an anticaking agent. For a very long period, synthetic amorphous silica was additionally utilised as an anticaking agent. For the purpose of preventing caking, granular and powdered meals have also included ingredients such as sodium silicate, sodium bicarbonate, calcium aluminosilicate, and aluminium silicate.[92]

- Gelling Agents

Nanostructures can be employed as gel-forming components in the food processing industry to enhance the feel of food. Active packaging for chicken fillet and cheese was studied using chitosan nanotechnology with a gelatine-based composite and Zinc oxide nanoparticles. A study created a gelatine-based composite that combines ZnONPs with CHNF and demonstrates potent antibacterial activity against bacteria that cause foodborne illness.[93], [94]

- Anti-oxidant Agents

Antioxidants are a class of chemicals that neutralise harmful free radicals by combining with them. This reduces stress and is crucial for the cure of illnesses caused by free radicals. Nevertheless, limited absorption, difficulties bridging cell membranes, and disintegration after delivery limit the efficacy of antioxidants. They, therefore, have a constrained amount of accessibility in the body. In order to circumvent these limitations, antioxidants have been covalently linked or packed into nanoparticles of different sources to improve stability, regulated dispersion, biological suitability, and targeted distribution.[95] It is believed that polymeric nanoparticles are well suited for encasing bioactive substances that are released in acidic conditions such as vitamins and flavonoids. Browning, an adverse consequence of phenolic chemicals converting to dark-coloured pigments in the oxygen-rich environment during marketing and storage, can be avoided by employing edible coatings in conjunction with antioxidant treatments on freshly cut fruit.[96]

IV. FOOD BIOSAFETY- NANOSENSORS

Alteration in food colour and the release of off-odoring gases during spoiling may both be detected via the application of nanosensors.[97] They are a device that can convert changes in the environment, such as those in light, heat, moisture, gas, and chemicals, into electric signals and have a data analysis component and a sensor component. The high sensitivity and selectivity of nanosensors make them superior to conventional sensors.[98] The sensors are particularly sensitive to gases including hydrogen, nitrogen oxides and ammonia. These gas sensors are made out of precious metals.[99]

4.1 Identification of food pathogenic bacteria

Common methods for identifying potentially dangerous microorganisms in food include sequencing or recognising entire bacterial cells. Using magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, the DNA of the milk-pathogenic bacterium *Listeria monocytogenes* was extracted. The amount of *L. monocytogenes* DNA in the milk sample was measured using PCR.[100] PCR-based microbial detection frequently use the 16s rRNA as a selective marker. Polymerase chain reaction-based assays are expensive, while those based on 16s rRNA microarrays are insensitive. Nevertheless, 16s rRNA may be detected in a simple and very sensitive way using nanoparticles.[101]

4.2 Identification of food-contaminating toxins

Food infected with *Aspergillus flavus* or *Aspergillus parasiticus* may contain aflatoxins, a class of poisonous and carcinogenic chemicals. Chemically modified gold NP containing anti-aflatoxin Ab were used for aflatoxin B1 detection.[102] Aflatoxin M1 in milk samples has also been detected using superparamagnetic beads incorporating anti-aflatoxin M1 Ab and Au-nanoparticles. Aflatoxin M1 in milk has been detected using an immunochromatographic strip approach that relies on gold nanoparticles. A colourless zone represents the aflatoxin M1-contaminated milk sample, whereas a red colour band indicates the lack of aflatoxin M1.[103] Specifically, the marine toxin palytoxin is commonly found in tainted seafood. Ultrasensitive screening of palytoxin in mussel flesh has been developed using electrochemiluminescent sensors based on carbon nanotubes.[104].

4.3 Identification of chemical and pesticide residues

Gold NP has been used as a colorimetric and fluorometric sensor for the detection of organophosphorus and carbamate pesticides. To identify the pesticide paraoxon, researchers have experimented with CdSe and CdSe-ZnS core-shell QDs.[105] Voltammetric biosensors have been developed using the selective binding of the insecticide parathion to a ZrO₂/Au nanocomposite sheet electrode. It was reported that harmful cadmium ions may be detected using MWCNT-Si composite-based potentiometer sensors.[106] Melamine in cow milk and newborn formulae was detectable by fluorescence sensors based on gold nanoparticles down to picomolar doses.[107] Using MWCNT-ionic liquid nanocomposites on carbon-ceramic electrodes, the food dyes sunset yellow and tartrazine were identified.[108] Sugar, dry fruits, and wine have all had sulfite detected using cobalt nitroprusside nanoparticles.

Chloramphenicol in honey has been detected using poly(EGDMA) nanoparticles.[109] MWCNTs have been used to detect Sudan I tampering in chilli powder. It has been shown that a SWCNT or MWCNT-zinc oxide nanocomposite can detect both bisphenol A and Sudan I at once. Plastic containers leach the hazardous chemical bisphenol A into the environment.[110] Consumer Price Index (CPI) is used as a proxy in this study for inflation rate. CPI is a wide basic measure to compute usual variation in prices of goods and services throughout a particular time period. It is assumed that rise in inflation is inversely associated to security prices because Inflation is at last turned into nominal interest rate and change in nominal interest rates caused change in discount rate so discount rate increase due to increase in inflation rate and increase in discount rate leads to decrease the cash flow's present value (Jecheche, 2010). The purchasing power of money decreased due to inflation, and due to which the investors demand high rate of return, and the prices decreased with increase in required rate of return (Iqbal et al, 2010).

4.4 Evaluation of Food Quality Caused by Improper Storing

By encouraging the antioxidant oxidation, oxygen supports the proliferation of microbes. For this reason, a methylene blue/TiO₂ nanocomposite material was crafted and used to create colorimetric oxygen indicators.[111] Luminescent poly(styrene-block-vinylpyrrolidone) nanobeads were also used to create an oxygen sensor. Trimethylamine is produced as a waste product during the extended digestion of animal proteins.[112] Hence, the presence of trimethylamine is indicative of deterioration in quality. The identification of trimethylamine in fish specimens was accomplished with the use of SnO₂-ZnO nanocomposite sensors.[113]

4.5 Nanobarcodes for product authenticity

All across the world, barcodes may be seen on the packaging of real goods. Widely used two-dimensional barcodes are easier to forge or destroy because of their accessibility. Nanoparticle-based hidden barcodes have the advantage of being difficult to forge.[114] There have been reports of novel nanoparticle-based encoding methods and nanodisk codes. The nanodisk code is a series of disc pairs created via surface-enhanced Raman scattering and readable by a Raman microscope. It has been reported on the existence of linear arrays of nanodisk codes made of gold, silver, and silver-gold heterodimers. Possible enhancements include the use of nanodisk codes consisting of disc pairs with multiple metal formulations and their chemical alteration with numerous types of chromophores.[115] Barcode nanorods based on fluorescent PPV have been created to be used in the tagging of individual packages.[116] Several researchers have claimed success in using fluorescent DNA dendrimer micro barcodes to identify dangerous infections in food and biological samples.[117] Hence, nano barcodes based on robust nanoparticles are superior than conventional barcodes.

Compared to conventional sensors, nanosensors can detect germs, poisons, and adulterants much more quickly and accurately. Degradable dietary elements like vitamins and antioxidant compounds may be detected with great efficiency using nanoparticles. Nanoparticles are used in smart, robust packaging and as quality indicators for individual products. Brands may stay pure and unadulterated thanks to invisible nanobarcodes. Electronic noses and electronic tongues that use nanoparticles can now mimic human olfactory and gustatory abilities. As you can see, the role of nanoparticles in the food business is crucial.

V. TYPES OF FOOD PACKAGING

Nanotechnology has the most promising use in the food service business in the creation of state-of-the-art packaging for perishable commodities. Nanotechnology is already being used by businesses to develop packaging solutions for food with longer shelf lives and lower potential for contamination.[118] Using nanotechnology, microscopic particles were included in the sheet to facilitate the movement of certain gases across the plastic, including carbon dioxide, which would otherwise degrade the food's freshness and limit its shelf life. They are also investigating if the film may act as a blockade to prevent the spoilage of food by gases like oxygen and ethylene.

The most cutting-edge advancement in food packaging is active and intelligent packaging, which promises to improve food quality and safety while extending the shelf life of packaged goods. Several businesses and educational institutions are funding the study and development of intelligent and active packaging that can detect when its contents have been tampered with, adapt to shifting environmental circumstances, and mend any damage it may have sustained.[119] Most packaging today is made from non-biodegradable plastic polymers derived from petroleum. That's why it's such a big deal that these food containers don't biodegrade: they pollute the planet. Since reducing packaging waste and extending shelf life both enhance food quality, the use of biodegradable packaging materials, such as food-safe films made from renewable resources, might help relieve the waste problem.[120]

Yet, at the present time, bio-based materials are used only seldom for food packaging. This is because barriers and mechanical characteristics are low in natural polymers. In order to broaden their packaging uses, organic polymers were often combined with man-made polymers or chemically altered. Nanocomposites used to packaging are another nanotechnology that has the potential to lessen the amount of unnecessary packaging thrown away with processed goods.[121]

Fig.2: Types of Packaging

5.1 Bio-based Packaging

Biobased packaging, also known as biodegradable packaging films, are used to seal food goods and maintain their freshness, flavour, and nutritional value by limiting the transfer of moisture and/or the exchange of gases. These materials are regarded as more eco-friendly than the standard packaging films currently in use. Bio-based packaging, like conventional packaging, serves to insulate perishable foods from the damaging effects of air, moisture, and gases in the surroundings.[\[122\]](#) Biodegradable packaging films have the unique property of decomposing through the activity of living organisms, setting them apart from conventional packaging alternatives. As the degradation products are entirely natural, this form of packaging is typically seen as more eco-friendly. Due to the bio-based nanocomposite concept's success in the field of synthetic polymers, researchers have begun looking at nanocomposites made from natural polymers for use in food packaging.[\[123\]](#)

5.2 Improved Packaging

During the process of creating better packaging, nanomaterials are integrated into the polymer framework in order to boost the package's gas-repellent qualities and resistance to both moisture and temperature. Beer, edible oil, and fizzy drink bottles are made using nanocomposites, which are a class of polymers reinforced with nanoparticles.[\[6\]](#) This packaging consists of nano-coatings, nanolaminates, clay nanoparticles, and nanocrystals. Nano-coatings for food are extremely thin films of food-safe material used to block the transfer of mass between ingredients.[\[124\]](#) These coatings could act as gas, lipid, and moisture barriers. Aqueous film-forming solutions or molten compounds are used to accurately apply and produce coatings on the food product. A nano-laminate consists of at least two nanoscale layers of materials that are mechanically or chemically bonded together. One of the most efficient methods in nanolaminates is the deposition-by-layer method, in which electrically charged surfaces are coated with interstitial layers comprised of multiple nano-layers of different materials.[\[125\]](#)

5.3 Active Packaging

In order to increase product safety, active packaging is created using nanomaterials that interact with the food or the environment. Nanosilver, MgO, CuO, TiO₂, and CNT are also anticipated for application in antibacterial food packaging in the future. Kodak has developed and produced antimicrobial packaging for packaged foods that absorb oxygen.[\[6\]](#), [\[126\]](#), [\[127\]](#) Enzymes packaged between polyethylene films have also been produced for oxygen-scavenging packaging. Active packaging is a method of preventing the growth of microbes even after the product has been opened and re-wrapped. Nanocrystalline titania films are frequently utilised as UV absorbers (TiO₂). It has been shown that films coated with TiO₂ and subjected to sunlight are effective for killing faecal coli forms in water. Metal doping enhances TiO₂'s ability to absorb visible light and boosts its photocatalytic properties when exposed to UV light.[\[128\]](#)

5.4 Smart Packaging

Nanomaterials are employed in smart/intelligent packaging to detect biochemical or microbiological differences in the food, such as the growth of harmful bacteria or the release of spoiled-food gases. In the context of smart packaging, nanoparticles can serve as sensitive components in packing materials, relaying data on the state of the enclosed item. Nanosensors may respond to changes in outside stimuli in order to interact, inform, detect the product and guarantee its quality and safety.[\[119\]](#) Spoilage indications, oxygen indicators, product identification, and traceability are just some of the recent advancements in polymer nanomaterials for smart food packaging.

VI. ANTI-MICROBIAL ACTION MECHANISM OF NANOPARTICLES

To accomplish their antibacterial action, NPs must come into association with bacterial cells. The most well-known interactions include electrostatic attraction, van der Waals forces, etc.[\[129\]](#)–[\[132\]](#) The majority of nanomaterials exhibit antibacterial activity that may be ascribed to one or more of the following strategies: blocking energy transfer, generation of harmful ROS, photocatalytic degradation, enzyme suppression, and decreased DNA synthesis.[\[133\]](#), [\[134\]](#) Oxidative stress generated by ROS is a key antimicrobial action of NPs. The kinds of ROS are singlet oxygen (O₂), OH[•], H₂O₂, and O[•].[\[135\]](#), [\[136\]](#) In bacterial species, the equilibrium between the synthesis and elimination of ROS is established under basal circumstances, however, when ROS generation is abnormal, the redox condition in cell is changed and encourages oxidation. Oxidative stress is created by this imbalanced situation, which harms the bacterial cells' physical structure.[\[137\]](#), [\[138\]](#)

Subsequent research has revealed that ROS are essential for the interplay between DNA and microbial.[\[139\]](#) Furthermore, ROS are advantageous for boosting oxidative protein gene expression levels, which is a crucial factor in bacterial cell death.[\[140\]](#) Moreover, ROS have the ability to damage proteins and inhibit the action of some periplasmic enzymes that seem crucial for preserving the regular shape and physiological functions of bacterial cells.[\[141\]](#) Nanoparticles can generate ROS through a range of methods. The prevalent theory at the moment is the photocatalytic hypothesis. The active compounds necessary to sustain the microorganism's typical physiological and morphological capabilities are disrupted by the production of ROS.[\[142\]](#)

Fig. 3: Schematic Representation of the Anti-Microbial Action Mechanism of the Nanoparticles

VII. MIGRATION OF NP

Nanoclay and nanosilver-containing polymers have been the focus of most studies on the movement of nanoparticles in meals. The findings of migration testing may be utilised to establish whether or not nanocomposites may be employed in packaged foods due to the higher risk of consumer health damage induced by NP migration from nanocomposites and processed food systems to beverages and meals.^[143] Metals usually transfer from packing materials into meals. Migrating nanoparticles go through three distinct phases: diffusion, dissolution, and distribution within the food. In order to weigh the possible dangers of nanoparticles in food, it is essential to comprehend their mobility.^[53] It is likely that the encapsulated NP on the sample's surface is responsible for the first release of the nanoparticles, explaining the observed migration phenomena. The NP is subsequently dispersed by diffusion and embedding via a dual-sorption process. Nanoparticle migration might be affected by the physicochemical properties of other food components.^[144]

VIII. HEALTH RISKS AND SAFETY CONCERNS

The migration or seeping of nanoparticles into the product from the packaging raises serious concerns about the safety of consuming foods that have come into contact with nano packaging. Critical parameters include the nature of the packing material, the toxicity of the NM, the pace of migration, and the amount of absorption by the meal.^[145] Inhaling or absorbing larger amounts of these substances via the skin is exceedingly hazardous to one's health.^[146] The gastrointestinal tract, small intestine, kidneys, liver, and spleen are only some organs that might store these nanoparticles, resulting in negative health repercussions.^[147] Cautious considerations suggest that research is needed on a number of fronts, such as the migratory patterns of NSMs in a food structure, the toxic effects of nanoparticles in humans, and their possible repercussions on consumer well-being and safety and the environment.^{[2], [147]} It is imperative to discuss not just the potential perils, but also the toxicological concerns and environmental factors. The relevant rules and regulations will be enacted just for the purpose of addressing the current safety concerns, after which they will govern the whole food industry.^[148]

IX. REGULATORY BODIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY IN THE FOOD INDUSTRIES

The implementation and enactment of nanosystems in food is governed by a number of regulatory bodies, including the EFSA, the EPA, the FDA, the NIOSH, the OSHA, the USDA, the CPSC, and the USPTO.^[149] Compliance with laws regarding nanoparticle size is a source of consumer concern, and it is the duty of the European Parliament and Council. Nanoparticles used as additives in food must be consistently sized.^[66] Industries need to use the precautionary principle (PP) rigorously in order to reduce the prevalence of freely synthesized NM in food. The European Commission's Regulation on Food Law has outlined a number of requirements for nanoparticles used in the foodservice industry.^[150] According to the rules, engineered nanomaterials can't include any harmful substances, including heavy metals and mycotoxins.^[151]

According to the European Union's Framework Regulation 1935/2004, additives added to food must not alter its nutritional value or alter their flavour. It must be completely inactive so as not to hasten food spoilage or negatively impact human health.^[152] The Regulation also requires preliminary research into the dose-response and harmful effects of nanocomponents before they may be used in food. Those in charge of manufacturing nanotechnology-based products for use in the food sector are legally obligated to adhere to the restrictions established by the relevant regulatory authorities.^[153]

X. CONCLUSION

The integrity of perishable products has to be preserved at a constant optimal temperature, even while being transported or stored. When it comes to the freshness and longevity of the food, it all comes down to the packing. With the advent of nanotechnology, new opportunities for technical progress in food packaging have emerged. Regular packaging is given a boost in barrier qualities, thermomechanical strength, plasticity, and durability when nanoparticles are linked to a polymer to create nanomaterial packaging. Foodborne pathogens are prevented from spreading thanks to nanostructured materials. Nanosensors also warn and notify buyers about the authenticity and safety of the food they are purchasing.

Concerns have been voiced, however, about the possibility of nanoparticles migrating into meals that have been packed. The execution of nanomaterial in the food packing industry is hampered by a lack of clarity regarding its toxicity, a dearth of supportive evidence from clinical trials, and insufficient research into risk. Ultimately, appealing to customers is crucial to the widespread success of using nanotechnology in the food business.

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